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TA'LIMDA TILLARNI O'QITISHNING MUAMMO VA YECHIMLARI

**ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЯЗЫКОВОГО
ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ПУТИ ИХ РЕШЕНИЯ**

**PROBLEMS OF LANGUAGE
LEARNING AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM**

MAVZUSIDAGI XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA

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DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS AND THEIR IMPACT ON DEVELOPING ARABIC LANGUAGE TEACHING FOR NON-NATIVE SPEAKERS

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Abstract: Education has witnessed significant development with the emergence of digital educational platforms, especially in the field of language teaching. This research aims to study the impact of these platforms on developing Arabic language teaching for non-native speakers, through analyzing the reality of their use, identifying the educational benefits they provide, and the challenges facing teachers and learners in this context. The research adopts a descriptive analytical approach, examining previous studies and analyzing educational platform content. Results indicate that platforms with interactive elements are more effective, though challenges include connectivity issues and assessment difficulties. The study recommends designing specialized Arabic teaching platforms and providing comprehensive teacher training programs.

Keywords: Arabic language, non-native speakers, educational platforms, digital education, interactive learning, language teaching methodology, digital competencies

Annotatsiya: So‘nggi yillarda raqamli ta’lim platformalarining paydo bo‘lishi, ayniqsa til o‘qitish sohasida, ta’lim jarayonida sezilarli yutuqlarga olib keldi. Ushbu tadqiqot ona tili bo‘lmaganlarga arab tilini o‘qitishni rivojlantirishda mazkur platformalarning ta’sirini o‘rganishga qaratilgan bo‘lib, ularning amalda qanday qo‘llanilayotganini tahlil qilish, taqdim etayotgan ta’limiy foydalarini aniqlash va ushbu kontekstda o‘qituvchilar hamda o‘quvchilar duch kelayotgan muammolarni oydinlashtirishni maqsad qiladi. Tadqiqotda tavsifiy-analitik

yondashuv qo'llanilgan bo'lib, ilgari olib borilgan ilmiy ishlar va ta'lim platformalarining mazmuni tahlil qilinadi. Natijalarga ko'ra, interaktiv elementlarga ega platformalar samaraliroq bo'lib chiqmoqda, biroq ulardan foydalanishda internet aloqasi muammolari va baholashdagi qiyinchiliklar mavjud. Tadqiqot xulosasida arab tilini o'rgatishga ixtisoslashgan maxsus platformalarni ishlab chiqish hamda o'qituvchilar uchun keng qamrovli malaka oshirish dasturlarini tashkil etish tavsiya etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: arab tili, ona tili bo'lmagan o'rganuvchilar, ta'lim platformalari, raqamli ta'lim, interaktiv o'qitish, til o'qitish metodikasi, raqamli kompetensiyalar

Introduction

In light of global digital transformations and challenges posed by global crises, digital educational platforms have become one of the most important modern learning environments in various educational fields, especially language learning. They have provided extensive opportunities for teaching Arabic to non-native speakers through interactive and engaging methods.

Educational platforms today are no longer merely modern teaching tools but have become an essential part of the digital education system in light of rapid technological advancement. The importance of this study lies in highlighting the effectiveness of these platforms in enhancing language skill acquisition and achieving learning objectives among learners from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

Many studies have discussed this matter to understand how to use modern educational technology in developing the educational process to keep pace with the times. In recent years, electronic platforms have emerged in the educational and Arabic environment to keep pace with contemporary challenges, leading to reshaping teachers' roles and methods, especially in language teaching fields. In this context, it has become necessary for Arabic language teachers for non-native

speakers to possess digital professional competencies that enable them to employ modern technologies effectively to meet the diverse needs of learners in this era.

Research Problem

Despite the widespread adoption of digital educational platforms, their effectiveness in teaching Arabic to non-native speakers remains questionable, especially regarding content adaptation and Arabic language digitization, linguistic interaction, and supporting the four skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Another equally important challenge emerges, represented by the lack of digital and training competencies among many teachers, which negatively affects teaching quality, interaction with learners, and accurately measuring their progress.

These issues raise fundamental questions about the effectiveness of digital educational platforms in developing Arabic language teaching for non-native speakers, in light of these intertwined educational and technical challenges. The research problem is defined in the following question: What is the impact of using digital educational platforms on developing Arabic language teaching for non-native speakers?

Research Objectives

The study aims to achieve several objectives: identifying the most prominent educational platforms used in teaching Arabic to non-native speakers, evaluating the role of digital platforms in developing language skills, monitoring the challenges facing the use of these platforms in education, and providing recommendations to improve the effectiveness of these platforms in teaching Arabic.

Research Importance

The research carries both theoretical and practical importance. From a theoretical perspective, it contributes to enriching educational literature related to digital education and language teaching. Practically, it provides guidance for teachers and content designers on effective use of platforms in Arabic teaching. Additionally, it highlights the relationship between digital development and language teaching quality from a technological standpoint.

Research Methodology

The research adopts the descriptive analytical approach, through referring to previous studies, analyzing the content of several educational platforms, and collecting opinions of experts in the field of Arabic language teaching.

Theoretical Framework

Educational Platforms Definition

Ahmed Zeidan (2013) defined educational platforms as intensive electronic courses targeting a large number of students, consisting of presentations explaining the course delivered by professors and experts, reading resources, and interactive tests. These platforms are characterized by ease of use, providing interactive environments between teacher and learner, containing diverse educational activities with easy file uploading and sharing capabilities.

Examples of Educational Platforms

Several platforms have emerged for Arabic language teaching, including Rwaq Platform (www.rwaq.org), an Arabic platform offering open courses in various specializations including teaching Arabic to non-native speakers. Edraak Platform (www.edraak.org), created by Queen Rania Foundation, provides free Arabic courses. Lisani Platform (www.lisani.app) specializes in teaching Arabic to non-native speakers using interactive digital methods. Other notable platforms include Madrasa Platform, Busuu, Duolingo, and AlifBee, each offering unique approaches to Arabic language instruction.

Digital Professional Competency

Digital professional competency refers to a set of cognitive, technical, and behavioral abilities that allow teachers to activate technology in all stages of the educational process, from planning to evaluation, achieving teaching quality and enhancing interaction in various learning environments. This competency develops gradually through five stages: Digital Educational Awareness, Basic Digital Qualification, Specialized Technology Employment, Innovation in Digital Practices, and Leadership in Digital Education.

Previous Studies

Al-Otaibi (2021) indicated that using Rwaq platform contributed to increasing motivation among Arab and non-Arab learners toward learning Arabic. Yousef et al. (2019) confirmed the importance of interaction in electronic platforms in developing listening and speaking skills among Arabic learners. However, Al-Khatib (2020) discussed challenges of employing digital platforms, such as weak interactive content and difficulty in self-language assessment. Al-Zahrani (2022) showed that weak technical and training competencies among teachers negatively affect the effective activation of educational platforms.

Research Results

The study reveals several key findings. Educational platforms provide flexible learning opportunities rich in resources, with platforms containing interactive elements such as instant tests, self-assessment, and educational videos proving more effective. Among the most prominent challenges facing these platforms are weak internet connection and difficulty in individual assessment. The need for training teachers in designing interactive content also emerges as a critical factor. Regular training and technical support are considered main factors contributing to improving teacher performance in digital learning environments.

Research Recommendations

The study recommends designing educational platforms specifically for teaching Arabic that consider learners' cultural and linguistic differences, developing technical and educational support tools for teachers during lesson implementation through digital platforms. It suggests integrating artificial intelligence elements to customize content and assessment, including specialized training programs to build teachers' competencies in employing educational platforms. Additionally, providing training for teachers on effectively using educational platforms and permanent linguistic support for learners within these platforms, such as chat with a teacher or language assistant, is recommended.

Conclusion

This research has shown that digital educational platforms represent a powerful and promising tool in teaching Arabic to non-native speakers, provided

they are activated in a studied educational manner that considers learners' needs and benefits from modern technological capabilities. The success of these platforms depends largely on proper implementation, teacher training, and addressing technical challenges to create effective learning environments for Arabic language acquisition.

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